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Research Quality Symposium

Book of Abstracts

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Sošice, Croatia

OPENING REMARKS

Dear guests,

It's a real pleasure to welcome you to the Research Quality Symposium here in the beautiful Žumberak Nature Park. Over the next two days, we'll reflect on how we can strengthen research quality, integrity, and impact.

We're delighted to bring together such a diverse group of researchers, publishers, funders, librarians, and infrastructures. We especially welcome early-career researchers. By convening such a wide range of voices, we aim to foster open dialogue, stimulate collaboration, and identify actionable steps toward a more transparent, reproducible, and inclusive research system.

Our program is rich: from plenary talks on reproducibility, open science, and AI, to short talks and workshops on data sharing, publishing, research assessment, and more. At the end of the second day, we will turn our focus to the Croatian research landscape and the specific opportunities and challenges we face here.

Beyond the sessions, I encourage you to take this time to connect, share experiences, and build collaborations. The setting and the community we've gathered here provide a perfect backdrop for meaningful conversations.

We would like to thank our funder, the Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ), for making this event possible and free for everyone. We also thank the Public Institution "Žumberak – Samoborsko gorje Nature Park" for providing the venue and some of their accommodation free of charge.

On behalf of the organizing team, thank you to all our speakers, participants, and supporters. We're excited for the discussions ahead and for the chance to work together toward better, more inclusive research.

I wish you all a successful and fulfilling experience.

*Dr. sc. Antica Čulina
Senior research associate
Ruđer Bošković Institute*

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PLENARY TALKS

Dr. sc. Tracey L. Weissgerber: *TREASURE: Rewarding graduate students for implementing reproducible, reusable and open research practices*

Abstract: This talk introduces a new program, TREASURE, that is being developed at the University of Coimbra to reward graduate students for implementing reproducible, reusable and open practices in their thesis research. After sharing the program structure, the talk will introduce some of the practices and outputs that students will be rewarded for implementing and share the challenges of adapting these criteria for different fields. Long-term goals include normalizing the implementation of reproducible, reusable and open research practices both for graduate students, and for others in their research groups.

Bio: Tracey Weissgerber was originally trained as a physiologist, before transitioning into metascience. Her research explores opportunities to improve transparency, rigor and reproducibility in research publications, with specific interests in improving data visualization and reporting of methods, and using automated screening tools to provide authors with feedback on published papers. Her team is also developing programs to reward graduate students for implementing open, reproducible and reusable practices in their thesis research. Dr. Weissgerber's educational work includes hands-on courses and summer schools, where participants immediately apply what they have learned to their own research.

Assoc. Prof. Goran Delač: *Integrating AI into the Scientific Method: Opportunities and Challenges*

Abstract: This talk explores how artificial intelligence (AI) is reshaping scientific research, from hypothesis generation to publication, and collaboration. While AI tools can potentially accelerate discoveries and their dissemination, they also raise important questions about bias, overdependence on AI systems, ethical responsibility, and broader social effects. We will examine the benefits and limitations of integrating AI into the scientific process, and discuss strategies to harness its power responsibly.

Bio: Goran Delač is an associate professor at the University of Zagreb Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing. His work focuses on artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, and their application in scientific and engineering domains, with a particular emphasis on AI explainability and transparency. He has actively contributed to projects focused on developing interpretable AI models to support robust and trustworthy services across various sectors, including fintech applications.

SHORT TALKS

Prof. Livia Puljak: *Systematic reviews: causing but also preventing research waste*

Abstract: This talk explores the paradoxical role of systematic reviews in contemporary research. While systematic reviews are essential tools for evidence synthesis and for guiding clinical and policy decisions, their rapid and sometimes redundant proliferation can contribute to research waste. The session will examine how poorly justified or duplicative reviews may clutter the evidence landscape and mislead decision-makers. At the same time, the lecture will highlight how well-conducted, transparent, and methodologically sound systematic reviews serve as a cornerstone of evidence-based practice and an important safeguard against unnecessary or misguided research. Practical strategies for improving review quality and avoiding redundancy will be discussed.

Bio: Prof. Livia Puljak, MD, PhD, is the Head of the Center for Evidence-Based Medicine and Health Care at the Catholic University of Croatia. Her research focuses on evidence synthesis, research methodology, and improving the quality and transparency of biomedical research. She has published extensively in the field of systematic reviews and serves as a contributor to international initiatives aimed at reducing research waste and promoting evidence-based practice.

Dr. sc. Alfredo Sánchez-Tójar: *Leveraging community-driven meta-research for reliable meta-analyses*

Abstract: How reliable are meta-analyses in ecology and evolution? In this talk, we present findings from a series of community-driven meta-research projects conducted

through collaborative hackathons. Our analyses reveal substantial shortcomings in open science practices across the field, including low rates of data and code sharing, limited use of pre-registration, and general lack of transparency. In addition, we identify widespread methodological issues that may compromise the validity of a nonnegligible share of published meta-analyses. By leveraging community-driven meta-research, we aim to highlight key areas for improvement and to discuss how community-developed guidelines and checklists can help foster more transparent, reproducible, and methodologically sound meta-analytic research.

Bio: Dr. Alfredo Sánchez-Tójar is an evolutionary ecologist whose work bridges empirical ecology and evolution, evidence synthesis, and meta research. He combines traditional meta analyses to test ecological and evolutionary hypotheses with meta research to evaluate and improve research practices. Trained as an ornithologist, Alfredo has in recent years shifted focus from fieldwork to the broader challenges of scientific reliability and transparency. Driven by a passion for open and reliable science, he serves on the Board of Directors of the Society for Open, Reliable, and Transparent Ecology and Evolution (SORTEE), advocating for cultural and institutional reforms in research.

Dr. sc. Danijela Žanko: *Use of open data sets in evidence synthesis*

Abstract: This talk presents a simulation study comparing Open Data Meta-Analysis (ODMA) against Classical Meta-Analysis (CMA) in ecological research. Through extensive simulations across scenarios combining different effect sizes and heterogeneity levels, we evaluate how publication bias and p-hacking affect meta-analytic accuracy, precision, and heterogeneity estimation. Using sample size distributions typical of ecological studies, we examine whether meta-analyzing raw open data can overcome the systematic biases that plague traditional meta-analyses of published results.

Bio: Danijela Žanko holds a Master's degree in Pure Mathematics from Freie Universität Berlin and a doctorate in Population Genetics from the Max Planck Institute for Plant Breeding Research in Cologne. Currently a postdoc at the Ruđer Bošković Institute, her research focuses on meta-analytic methodology and evidence synthesis in ecological research. Her work examines how different approaches to meta-analysis can address systematic biases in published literature, combining mathematical rigor with practical applications for improving research reliability in ecology and evolution.

Dr. sc. Jadranka Stojanovski: *Quality, Integrity and Equity in Diamond Open Access Publishing*

Abstract: In response to the ongoing crisis in scholarly publishing new priorities and initiatives have emerged. Among the most significant is Diamond Open Access publishing model. This community-driven, academic-led, and non-commercial approach eliminates fees for both authors and readers. While Diamond OA is already the dominant model in some countries, the value and impact of these journals are still insufficiently recognised. Through the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects, efforts have been directed toward supporting editors of Diamond journals, who face challenges such as sustaining editorial quality, ensuring transparency and research integrity, and coping with limited financial resources. To address these needs, the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) was launched. EDCH reinforces the Diamond OA community by supporting institutional, national, and disciplinary centres, publishers, and service providers. Its online platform (<https://diamas.org/>) provides services, tools, and best practices. Community-governed and openly accessible, EDCH empowers Diamond OA publishers to thrive without costly external support. By fostering collaboration, equity, and sustainability, it ensures that high-quality research remains transparent, trustworthy, and accessible worldwide.

Iva Grabarić Andonovski: *DEI and sustainability in research publishing*

Abstract: When we are considering research quality, much attention is given to the data quality, presentation, and evaluation of research outputs. However, other critical factors, such as diversity, equity, inclusivity (DEI) and sustainability, are equally relevant for achieving the responsible and impactful research. In this talk, you will hear more about the ways in which DEI principles and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) can be implemented into the research practices. The important role that publishers can play in supporting researchers through guidelines and initiatives that promote DEI and sustainability to achieve more impactful research environment, but also contribute to more robust, innovative, and globally relevant outcomes, will be highlighted.

Bio: Iva Grabarić Andonovski is the Editor of Food Technology and Biotechnology, one of the leading diamond open access scholarly journals in Croatia. She is one of the founders and current President of the Croatian Association for Scholarly Communication (CROASC or ZNAK in Croatian), Vice President as well as Chair of Croatian Regional Chapter and Co-Chair of Environment and Sustainability Committee of the European Association of Science Editors (EASE), member of HRČAK Advisory Board, and a

member of OPERAS Special Interest Group on Best Practices. Her focus is on best practices and sustainability in diamond open access scholarly publishing.

Assoc. Prof. Ksenija Baždarić: *Attitudes towards preprinting in Croatian authors*

Abstract Chalmers and Glasziou estimated that 85% of research is wasted due to inadequate research design or methodology, poor reporting, publication bias, and lack of scholarly openness, with some viewing preprint servers as a way to address some of these issues. Preprinting is an open science practice that allows the deposition and distribution of manuscripts (preprints) using an open science infrastructure (thematic or general preprint server) before submitting to a journal and being formally peer-reviewed. There are more than 60 preprint servers covering all scholarly fields, and the number of preprints is rising. Preprints are seen as a step toward greater openness of science and many journals and funders today encourage preprinting and Scopus and Dimensions have started indexing preprints. Studies evaluating attitudes towards preprinting are few and in this talk I will address attitudes towards preprints in Croatian academics (2020) and biomedical authors in the Croatian Medical Journal (2024).

Bio: Ksenija Baždarić is associate professor at the Department of Basic Sciences Rijeka University Faculty of Health Studies, Croatia. Her academic background lies both in social sciences and biomedicine. She is the Editor-in-Chief of the European Science Editing (EASE journal) and European Journal of Health Studies (Faculty of Health Studies University of Rijeka journal) and research integrity editor in the Croatian Medical Journal.

Luka Ursić: *Image manipulation in research: how well does the human eye detect duplications?*

Abstract: Image manipulation, whether accidental or purposeful, has been flagged as a significant problem in research – one exacerbated by the emergence of paper mills and their misuse of emerging artificial intelligence-based tools. In our study at a medical school in Croatia, we found that both students and experts had difficulties detecting duplications in images of Western blots, cell cultures, and histological sections extracted from published research articles. In this talk, we will discuss the implications of our

findings for scholarly publishing and discuss them in the context of recent research on the extent of image manipulations in science.

Bio: Luka Ursić works at the University of Split School of Medicine as a research assistant funded by the Croatian Science Foundation. His PhD focuses on the transparency and completeness of reporting in health system guidelines for pandemics. He has freelanced as an editor for several scholarly journals, through which he performed research on topics related to ethics and integrity in scientific publishing. He is also the co-chair of the Croatian Reproducibility Network, where he participates in research and outreach activities.

Dr. sc. Jadranka Stojanovski: *Reforming research assessment - COARA*

Abstract: The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) is a global movement of universities, funders, academies, and research organisations working to change how researchers and research are evaluated. Instead of relying on journal impact factors or rankings, it promotes fairer, more transparent assessment that values quality, openness, collaboration, and diverse contributions—from mentoring and peer review to data sharing and societal impact. For researchers, this means more freedom to pursue meaningful work and broader recognition of what really matters in science. The CoARA Working Group on Recognising and Rewarding Peer Review develops recommendations to acknowledge peer review as a fundamental scholarly contribution alongside research and teaching. By embedding peer review into recognition and reward systems, the academic community can foster higher-quality reviews, strengthen research integrity, and create a more transparent and sustainable ecosystem that values the full range of scholarly contributions.

Asist. Prof. Serge P. J. M. Horbach: *Reforms in editorial peer review*

Abstract: While editorial peer review practices and procedures have always been a homogeneous mix of diverse approaches, the system is currently going through yet another wave of reform and innovation. In this talk, we will discuss several main changes to the system, including the shifting roles of reviewers and editors in the editorial process, the transition to openness and transparency in review, and the emergence of new technologies to support editorial tasks. We will also comment on drivers of these changes and the potential consequences.

Bio: Serge P. J. M. Horbach is an assistant professor at the Institute for Science in Society, Radboud University, the Netherlands. He has a background in mathematics and obtained a phd in sociology of science, studying matters of research integrity and scholarly communication. In his current work, he focusses on innovations in research assessment, particularly in editorial processes; open science practices; and science-society interactions, particularly related to public trust in science.

Assoc. Prof. Ivana Bosnic: *Open data analysis as a form of student education for wider societal benefits*

Abstract: The Open Data Portal of the Republic of Croatia hosts around three thousand open data sets. The data covers a wide range of topics, comes in various formats, and also varies greatly in quality, which directly affects its usability and suitability for reuse. The Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing of the University of Zagreb (FER) has been offering the course *Open Computing* for several decades. The course introduces students to the concepts of openness in various areas of computing, from highly technical to social aspects. In recent years, one of the course activities involves students analyzing open data sets available on the Portal. Each student chooses five different data sets and analyzes them, and suggests potential improvements. All student comments are submitted to the Portal, where they are forwarded to the publishers for further review and possible modification. This activity provides data publishers with feedback from "real users," while giving students a sense of usefulness and teaching them responsibility for the analyses they write. Overall, this is a societally beneficial activity that encourages civic engagement and, at least to some extent, improves the quality of open data sets, which can be important for enhancing quality of life in certain aspects.

Bio: Ivana Bosnić, PhD, is an Associate Professor at the University of Zagreb, Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, Croatia. Her primary research interests include open computing with an emphasis on open data, software engineering education, data literacy, and e-learning, especially open educational resources and technologies. Her recent (open) data projects include Horizon2020 TODO - Twinning Open Data Operational and Erasmus+ DIRECTORS - Digital data-driven Education for kids.

Asist. Prof. Ljerka Ostojić: *Open Science in Higher Education: Why Starting Early is Key*

Abstract: Open Science principles and tools are usually the topic of postgraduate programmes, with many initiatives being aimed at PhD students and postdoctoral researchers (commonly referred to as Early Career Researchers). We argue that this is too late and that research integrity questions and Open Science in particular should be embedded into teaching and research at least at the Masters level. We consider two reasons: first, a big portion of academic research is conducted by Masters students, and second, Open Science transcends academic research and is considered an important aspect for industry and society as a whole. In this talk, we will present how we have integrated Open Science principles into a research-focused Masters programmes and why it is important to also incorporate critical Open Science perspectives when teaching about research integrity and conducting research. We will present both the lecturers' perspectives and experiences, as well as outcomes of our students' work.

Bio: I research how humans and non-human animals perceive and interact with other individuals. A secondary line of my research is focused on how we produce, report, and discuss research, specifically in my study area but also more generally (often referred to as meta-science). I started off studying psychometrics during my Bachelors and Masters studies in Psychology at the University of Vienna, before moving to the University of Cambridge where I obtained a PhD in Experimental Psychology working on comparative cognition. Since 2020 I am an Assistant Professor at the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences at the University of Rijeka, where I am currently Head of the Division of Cognitive Sciences and a member of the Department of Psychology.

Dr. sc. Matt Grainger: *Open Science for Early-career Ecologists – The Living Norway PhD course*

Abstract: How do we equip early-career researchers with the tools, mindset, and support needed to practice open, reproducible, and transparent science? Through the Living Norway Ecological Data Network, we have developed and delivered an intensive PhD-level course designed to meet this challenge. In this talk, I reflect on our experience designing and teaching this course (covering FAIR data principles, reproducible workflows, and open publishing) highlighting what worked, what surprised us, and what still needs to change to make open science the default in ecology.

Bio: Matt Grainger is a researcher at the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research, where he focuses on biodiversity, wildlife management, and evidence synthesis. He is a co-developer and -instructor of the Living Norway PhD course on open, reproducible, and transparent science in ecology. His work aims to build capacity for open science practices in ecological research and education, with an emphasis on practical tools and cultural change.

Dr. sc. Ivan Fliš: *Philosopher's perspective on research waste*

Abstract: Research waste is the quantifiable estimate of the amount of information lost during the life cycle of research. Meta-scientists and in particular meta-analysts have sounded the alarm over the last decade as their estimates indicate very high levels of waste (e.g. over 80% in ecology and medicine). In turn, they recommend methodological and institutional reforms to reduce waste in the literature. In this short talk, I will try to sketch a brief historical picture of the network of academic institutions that produced, housed, maintained and sold access to literature. The institutions in question have developed in the twentieth century: the publishing industry that focuses on the publication of scientific articles, the funding institutions that financially support scientific research, and the development of gold-standard statistical concepts of procedural objectivity within certain scientific communities (in my examples, biomedicine and scientific psychology). My aim is to open up the discussion not only about the assessment of waste and its possible solution, but also about the complex network of causes that produce it in the first place. I think that such historical sketches, which are sociologically sophisticated and philosophically significant, provide empirical scientists with material for discussions about the efficacy of their research, the rigor of their communities, and the goals that should guide science as an endeavor. If I am persuasive, the wastefulness of the metascientists who try to estimate it quantitatively will turn out to be a feature, not an undesirable consequence, of the system of science in which we work. Whether we want such a system and find its products desirable is a whole other discussion, which I hope we will begin (and continue) later today.

Bio: Ivan Fliš is a postdoctoral researcher in the ERC-funded project REVENANT at the Faculty of Philosophy and Social Sciences at the University of Rijeka. His work in REVENANT investigates more than a century of reception of the life and work of Nikola Tesla. Ivan holds a BA and MA in psychology from the University of Zagreb, and a PhD in history and philosophy of science from Utrecht University. His PhD research focused on the history and philosophy of the so-called replication crisis in psychology, and he continues to think and talk about replication, history and philosophy of statistics, and

history of psychology as a lecturer in the Cognitive Sciences Master's at the University of Rijeka.

Dr. sc. Ivica Vilibić: *Two tales on gaining 'benefits' through 'publish or perish'*

Abstract: This talk will explore how researchers and publishers in the geosciences adapt under two boundary conditions: (1) when the research and academic system is dominantly driven by 'publish or perish' principles, as is the case in Croatia; and (2) when a catastrophic event, such as the explosive eruption of the Hunga Tonga–Hunga Ha'apai volcano in 2022, triggers a wave of rapid publishing in prestigious and less prestigious journals. In the first case, it appears that personal gain significantly drives Croatian researchers toward rapid-review, 'gray-zone' journals and publishers such as MDPI. In the second, globally impactful and extreme events result in a race to publish, from which both researchers and journals benefit—particularly those at the top-tier level, such as Nature and Science. Both tales reveal troubling trends that run against the responsible research practices on which science should be built, raising questions about the integrity of current evaluation systems and publication policies.

Bio: Ivica Vilibić is a senior research scientist at the Ruđer Bošković Institute and the Institute of Adriatic Crops and Karst Reclamation, with a background in oceanography, meteorology, and climate science. He has authored over 150 peer-reviewed papers, reviewed more than a hundred research projects and publications, and served as leader or collaborator in numerous national and international projects. He is also actively involved in community-driven initiatives—ranging from research integrity to various geoscience programs—and has served as chair, member or delegate in many national and international committees and bodies.

DISCUSSIONS

Dr. Antica Čulina: A framework to improve research quality across disciplines

Abstract: The research quality and impact are reduced in the current research, funding, and publishing system. Within the project EcoOpen, we are developing a decision-making framework aimed at helping researchers, support staff, funders, and publishers to inform themselves about the existing issues and their magnitude, and about the potential actions they can take to mitigate or eliminate these issues. The framework is largely evidence-based. During this session, I will present the current version of the framework, and then take the opportunity to discuss it with the audience.

Round table: Improving research quality & impact in Croatia

Chair: Antica Čulina

Panel: Dario Lečić (HRZZ), Ljerka Ostojić (Uni Rijeka), Livia Puljak (Croatian Catholic University), Iva Grabarić Andonovski (PBF), Luka Ursić (University of Split), Goran Delač (FER), Iva Melinščak Zlodi (FFZG)

Abstract: Improving research quality and impact will depend on both the global setup of the research, funding, promotion, and publishing systems, as well as on the country-level specific challenges and opportunities. In this roundtable, we will discuss the specifics of the Croatian landscape with a diverse set of panelists.

WORKSHOPS

Shreya Dimri: *Reproducible Manuscripts with Quarto*

Abstract: Transparency and reproducibility are fundamental aspects of good research practices. While replicating scientific findings can be challenging, computational reproducibility —particularly the outputs reported in a manuscript —must be entirely reproducible. In this workshop, we will learn to set up a reproducible workflow to create a publication-ready manuscript that combines data, analyses, text, figures and references into a single final output.

We will use the Quarto publishing system in combination with R (or Python) to create a reproducible manuscript. More specifically, we will talk about:

- What Quarto? Why Quarto? — Pros and Cons of using Quarto Manuscripts
- Project Structure for transparency
- Using Markdown and Inline code for writing text
- Using Code Chunks and embedding outputs to create figures, tables
- Manage references using Zotero or BibTeX
- Render our Quarto Project to Docx, HTML, pdf files

This workflow is aimed at reducing the amount of human error, improving computational reproducibility and making updating scientific manuscripts more efficient. If you have used R-Markdown before, think of Quarto as its more powerful successor. It has the potential to be able to enhance transparency of a project and make it more accessible to other researchers.

Expectations for the workshop

This workshop is designed to be an introduction to the Quarto manuscript system. Participants must be familiar with some coding language (R or Python) and Markdown. Part of the workshop will be a presentation, followed by a demonstration of the workflow. It is not mandatory to bring your laptops, but participants are encouraged to follow along. If you would like to do so, please ensure you have Quarto installed, along with R-Studio.

Marija Purgar: *Automated assessment of transparency of scientific literature*

Abstract: Transparent reporting practices, including study registration, conflict of interest and funding disclosures, and data and code availability statements, are essential for ensuring credibility and improving the reproducibility of research. However, assessing these practices across the scientific literature remains challenging, particularly at scale.

This workshop introduces a user-friendly text mining tool developed to automatically screen research articles for key transparency indicators listed above. Participants will learn how to apply the tool to full-text articles in PDF or PMC XML format and extract transparency-related information in a standardized and scalable way. The tool was developed for ecological and evolutionary research but can be readily adapted to other disciplines.

The workshop is designed for early-career researchers looking to embed open science practices into their work, open science advocates aiming to monitor community progress, journal editors and publishers interested in tracking compliance with transparency guidelines, and funders evaluating reporting standards across funded outputs.

What to expect

- A brief overview of the tool's development, validation, and use cases
- A live demonstration of how to apply the tool to research articles
- Guided hands-on work with either participant-provided PDFs or a curated sample set

What to bring

A laptop and 5–10 full-text research articles (PDF or PMC XML) you are interested in screening for transparency. A set of 10 pre-selected PDFs will also be available for participants who do not bring their own materials. No programming experience is required.

Symposium website
<https://rqi.irb.hr/symposium>

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